
An Investigative Study of Rationality and Forgiveness

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Abstract:

This attempt is to make investigation study to describe the relationship between forgiveness, rationality among undergraduate students from Pune. The major objectives of this study are to see the relationship among forgiveness and rationality to explore the impact of irrational belief on forgiveness and lastly to investigate the role of gender and region on forgiveness and irrational belief in student community of Pune came from various parts of India. The data collection done on a sample of 149 undergraduate students studying in Pune from rural and urban regions with the help of Irrational Belief Inventory (IBI) & Heartland Forgiveness Scale (HFS). The outcome of the research indicate that irrational belief is negatively correlated with the forgiveness. It is also observed that Females (girls) are more of irrational belief than the males (boys). Rural or urban region of participants doesn't have major impact on forgiveness and irrational behavior. This study has given need to include the rationality in the education for development of forgiveness among the students.

Keywords – Irrational belief, Rationality, Forgiveness, Undergraduate Students

Introduction:

Positive psychology has tremendous importance in the speedy life of Pune. India is known country of bundle of various religions and customs until today. It is also registered in the history if any specific religious actions are predominant in the society; the revolutionary actions by various social reformist have been taken up. However, the purpose is to maintain the secular status of the country has to be remain intact. The country has placed its positions by presenting the rational attitude in various critical situation by forgiveness and balanced society. Almost in all indian philosophies and teachings, we always support to forgiveness. This was possible as we maintained for secular approach throughout the history of humankind. Forgiveness and rational behavior are few important attributes of Indian society. The

forgiveness is the attitude to release the painful incidences and thoughts in order to maintain the mental peace and work with benefit of every individual. With more rational approach we can become successful in our daily management of relations. We can see the benefit of such behavior in our country by numerous philosophers.

Irrational Belief:

It is a central idea in cognitive theories and therapies in the various abnormal behavioral & disorders like depression, anxiety. Due to irrational beliefs, depressed and anxious persons conclude the situations incorrectly and report in wrong way. Looking at the seriousness and implications in treatments and its further consequences, we all must work very systematic way to analyze the behavior. Even the irrational belief assessment is very

important, there have been urgency to see the connection between the irrational beliefs and other positive psychology constructs. Most of the tests of irrational beliefs developed thus far have grown out of the work of Ellis, who developed rational-emotive behavior therapy or REBT, and Beck, who was instrumental in creating cognitive therapy or CT. The rational behavior leads to positive outcomes.

Forgiveness:

Forgiveness was earlier seen as a part of religiosity or spirituality. But it is seen it is more than just spiritual content and we can see the roots of it in mental balance and emotional stability (Enright 2001, Luskin 2003). Forgiveness means abandoning negative thoughts or behaviors when faced with injustice; in some cases, it means having a positive attitude (Rye and Pargament 2002). There are different types of forgiveness. Forgiveness because of the other person experiencing the same thing that has happened to him is vengeful forgiveness. It is conditional forgiveness for a person to forgive on the condition of getting back what he has lost. Forgiveness for the expectations of others is expectation-oriented forgiveness. Forgiveness that prioritizes social peace is forgiveness for social harmony. Forgiveness full of love for the sake of continuing the relationship. Forgiveness due to religious/philosophical views is conscientious forgiveness (Enright, Santos, and Al-Mabuk 1989). According to Enright and Fitzgibbons (2000), it might take a certain amount of time before a person can forgive. According to them, real forgiveness is out of the question in attitudes and behaviors such as condoning, ignoring, reconciling, leaving it to time, caring about its interests and verbally saying that one forgives. Studies have shown that forgiveness has positive effects on a person's psychological well-being.

Literature Review:

Bayat et.al. investigated the comparison of the effectiveness of training based on rational, emotional and behavioral therapy (REBT) and acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT) on forgiveness of women affected by marital infidelity with quasi experimental with pretest-posttest and follow-up with designed control group.

Uzma Parveen & Reetika Pal (2024) studied the relationship between forgiveness, emotional regulation and resilience in young adults facing adversity. It was seen by them, a significant moderate positive relationship between forgiveness and resilience, supporting the hypothesis that forgiveness contributes to resilience in young adults.

Thomas & Kamble (2023) examined the relationship between forgiveness with social connectedness and subjective well-being. It was revealed, a positive and statistically significant correlation of forgiveness with social connectedness and Subjective well-being. It was also seen that forgiveness was a key component in predicting social connectedness and subjective well-being of the participants.

Monika & Lalita (2024) studied the existence of significant relationship between forgiveness and psychological wellbeing, gratitude and psychological wellbeing more in girls than the boys.

Toussaint et.al. (2023) examined the association between forgiveness and flourishing. Also studied the stress-and-coping models of forgiveness of oneself and others. It was found that flourishing is due to several components like mental and physical health, happiness, meaning and purpose, social engagement, character and virtue, and financial and material stability other than forgiveness.

Rahmandani et.al. (2020) investigated forgiveness has a greater correlation with resilience in men than in women. Situation forgiveness had more correlation of all with resilience. Men are of

others forgiveness nature show higher correlation with resilience than self-forgiveness, whereas in women self-forgiveness had a higher correlation with resilience than forgiveness of others.

Momina Abeed & Sarwat Sultan (2015) examined predictive role of dispositional forgiveness and resilience among the women. It was found that positive significant impact on psychological resilience and dispositional forgiveness among women. It was also seen that marital status of women has major impact on it.

Rationale of the Study:

The life with rational behavior helps to navigate in various situations. But the most of the time we can observe that, people behave very irrational and they don't even notice also. The irrational belief creates trouble in the society and leads to unrest also in some situations. In against the if person demonstrate the rational behavior in regular walk of life, then his relations with surrounding situations remains healthy. It is observed that in earlier research the relationship between forgiveness and well being was examined in various ways and number of times. However, it was seen after literature review, the gap to connect the irrational belief and forgiveness. In addition, most of the research has happened with non-indian sample. If we look in the history, forgiveness has been taught in almost all philosophies. But somewhere we are not able develop that in our daily schedule. The correlational analysis between the irrational belief and forgiveness can guide to future research regarding the application of interventions based on forgiveness and its impact with rationality. Furthermore, in the implication of it will also propagate the urgency to work on irrational belief through various ways of training to generations like education.

Method:

Participants:

The participants in this study were 149 undergraduate students (99 Boys & 50 girls) studying professional courses in Pune City from various regions of India randomly selected. Pune is known to be oxford of east where students come for varied educations, regional, financial and cultural background. Here only the region of their residence is taken into consideration. The age group of participants was 18 to 22 years. The participants willingly ready to participate are taken for data collection.

Objectives:

1. To examine forgiveness and Irrational belief for the relationship among them.
2. To assess the effect Irrational belief on forgiveness.
3. To explore the differences among the Irrational belief and forgiveness with reference to gender and region.

Hypothesis:

1. Irrational belief is in negatively correlation with forgiveness.
2. Irrational belief has significant effect on forgiveness.
3. Rationality and forgiveness will be significantly more among males (boys) than the females (girls).

Tools Used:

The data was collected with the help of following psychological tools:

- Irrational belief Inventory (IBI)
- Heartland Forgiveness Scale (HFS)
- Irrational Belief Inventory (IBI)

Petra Koopmans, Robbert Sanderman, Irma Timmerman developed the Irrational Belief Inventory (IBI), Paul M.G. Emmelkamp (1994) derived from Rationality Inventor (RBI) and Irrational Belief Test (IBT). This inventory consists of 50 statements is used to measure for

establishing irrational belief systems. The Likert's method of summated ratings was used and the weightings on the five-point scale. Like Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Uncertain (3), Disagree (2), Strongly Disagree (1). The total score of the 50 statements of the IBI can be obtained by summing across all items. A high score reflects irrationality.

The scale divided in five subscales: worrying, rigidity, problem avoidance, demand for approval, emotional irresponsibility. These subscales correlate lowly to moderately strong to each other. The IBI has a good internal consistency for the subscales as well as for the total score. The reliability of Irrational Belief Inventory (IBI) subscales (range $\alpha = 0.7 - 0.85$) and total IBI scale ($\alpha = 0.85$) (N-536) was satisfactory.

Heartland Forgiveness Scale (HFS):

Thompson et. al. (2005) developed this scale used for assessment of dispositional forgiveness. This is 18 item scale that examine dispositional forgiveness in three subscales with six items each with self (6 items), others (6 items) and situations (6 items). Rating possibilities range from 'Almost Always False of Me' to 'Almost Always True of Me'. Scores on each subscale range from 6 to 42; total HFS scores range from 18 to 126. The score on the Total Heartland Forgiveness scale indicates how forgiving you tend to be, in general, of yourself, others, and negative uncontrollable circumstances. High score depicts higher levels of forgiveness, and low score depicts lower levels of forgiveness. Primary focus of this scale is self-forgiveness, composed of six items five of which entail self-condemnation and one of which marks to understanding oneself. The HFS Self and

HFS Other are good brief measures of two types of dispositional forgiveness.

Operational Definitions:

Irrational belief: Irrational belief is a total score obtained by the subjects on the Irrational Belief inventory (Koopmans et.al.). The total score ranges from 102 to 198. Few statements are framed in the rational manner to examine the inclination towards the rationality. Low score indicates rationality and high score indicates irrationality.

Forgiveness: Forgiveness is a total score obtained by the subjects on the Heartland Forgiveness Scale (Thompson et. al.). For each of the three subscales, scores of 31 are average, and on the Total Forgiveness scale, a score of 93 is average. Higher scores indicate higher levels of forgiveness, and lower scores indicate lower levels of forgiveness.

Procedure:

The questionnaire of two scales printed on separate sheets and response sheets are printed separately. The necessary information given briefly before the actual solving of the scale. The purpose and use of the data collected is narrated clearly and then willingness taken from each participant. The assurance about the confidentiality about the individual responses was given to all present respondents. The data was collected, processed to analyse as for the purpose of the study.

Results:

The analysis of data done using SPSS as well R-studio. Initially data was used to find the means and standard deviation (SD). By getting the values of the level of each variable i.e. irrational belief & forgiveness was compared with respect to gender and region of residence.

Table 1. Means & SD scores of forgiveness and Irrational belief on the basis of gender

Variable	Forgiveness	Irrational behavior
Male /Boys (N=99)	86.02 (11.46)	148.73 (14.42)
Female/Girls (N=50)	84.24 (11.82)	115.66 (13.47)
Total Students (N=149)	85.42 (11.57)	151.05 (14.44)

The descriptive statistics values (Mean, SD) of Forgiveness {85.42 (11.57)} and irrational belief {151.05 (14.44)} given in above Table (I). It shows that the intermediate levels of forgiveness, irrational

behavior. Male and females (girls) both represent same level of forgiveness. Whereas, forgiveness & irrational belief scores are more in males (boys) than that of females (girls).

Table 2. Means & SD scores of forgiveness, resilience, and Irrational belief on the basis of region (urban / rural)

Variable	Forgiveness	Irrational Behavior
Urban (N=93)	85.35 (11.33)	152.38 (13.97)
Rural (N=56)	85.54 (12.07)	148.86 (15.06)
Total (N=149)	85.43 (11.57)	151.05 (14.44)

Table (II) shows that the forgiveness level is almost similar both urban as well in

rural adults. Whereas, rural adults are more irrational than that of urban adults.

Table 3. Pearson correlation among three aspects of forgiveness

Variable	Self	Other	Situation based
Self	1		
Others	0.391	1	
Situation based	0.479	0.497**	1

**p<.01 *p<.05

Table (III) indicates the positive correlation for other and situation based forgiveness significant at 0.01 level.

Table 4. Pearson correlation among forgiveness and irrational behavior

Variable	Forgiveness	Irrational Behavior
Forgiveness	1	
Irrational Behavior	0.0512**	1

**p<.01 *p<.05

Table (IV) shows that the correlation between the forgiveness and irrational belief significant at 0.01 level.

Discussions:

The India has great history of

philosophies as well the behaviour of people to make our nation more considerate for all

kind of religions, so our country is known to be secular country. The rational approach, in our culture has been, somewhere becomes invisible and more or less the irrationality has been increased in the society looking as the unrest in societal interactions. India also known to be youngest country of India. So more youngster has to be addressed to handle this situations,. But if we see the precisely the secular approach in society has made this possible which has considers everyone's religion and found the forgiving nature is deeply rooted in Indian adults. So we could see the society has power to come out of various adverse situations and come back to original position rather o make more stronger for such challenging situations in future. The society becomes more stronger with the base of such values and mindset. Even Indian constitution also said very precisely bout our secular structure.

Eventually we could see we see the change in the thoughts and behaviour of members of society. To see this changes, the present study is done on resilience, forgiveness and Irrational belief . The interactions and impact of each other also tried to find out in this study. It is observed the Indian men and women are of equal irrational belief even may be urban or rural region. It has helped to understand development of rationality will help to development of forgiveness among the younger generation to make more rational and peaceful, secular society.

When data was checked with reference to gender, it is observed that no significant difference in forgiveness among males (boys) and females (girls). It is equal level of forgiving nature considering the impact of improved level of education in country. However, males (boys) represent more rational behavior than that in females (girls). And in adverse situation the rural women have major impact on the family also compared to urban society.

The study of interrelation among

various dimensions of forgiveness, it was found that low positive correlation in forgiving for other and to situation. The correlation between the self-forgiveness and others-forgiveness as well self-forgiveness and situation-forgiveness was not clearly visible. The men and women both represent the attitude to forgive others and in turn, therefore to situation also. The results are confirming the earlier studies of forgiveness on the indian adults.

The irrational belief and forgiving nature are negatively corelated. It means, forgiveness decreases with increase in irrational belief and vice versa. In further investigation, it is seen that the rational behavior has been observed more in males (boys) as compared to females (girls) leads to increase in the forgiveness. The society need rationality which will impact forgiving nature. If we look into today's indian society, we need to impart through education the rational behavior to develop indian students and future citizens with more forgiving society irrespective of gender and region of location.

Limitations of the Study:

It was a small effort to examine the pattern of gender and region on forgiveness, Irrational belief among indian undergraduate students. Empirical work on forgiveness and irrational belief is helps generally the outcomes of these variables about their association. This study work completed using data collected from a very small sample of a limited population. The data can be collected from various religions to assess irrational belief as well the education background to see the effect of education on the variables can be possible to examine. Even this, the data in the study was done using only way of quantitative method. Hence, future studies could be organized with planned elimination of the current limitations such that the findings can be expanded on a larger and broader level.

References:

1. Annalakshmi, N., & Lijo, K. J. (2013). Relationship between resilience, gender and forgiveness among older adolescent students. *The recent trends in psychology*, 66-82.
2. Aziz, I. A., & Yildirim, M. (2019). Investigating Relationship Between Psychological Trait Resilience and Forgiveness Among Internally Displaced Persons. *Psychology, Community & Health*.
3. Bower, B. (1996). Rational mind design: research into the ecology of thought treads on contested terrain. *Science News*, 150, 24-25
4. Dawes, R. M. 1988. *Rational Choice in an Uncertain World*. San Diego: Harcourt. Evans, J. (1984). Heuristic and analytic processes in reasoning. *British Journal of Psychology*, 75, 451-468. Gigerenzer, G. (2000). *Adaptive Thinking: Rationality in the Real World*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
5. Samuels, R. and Stich, S. (2002). Rationality. In *Encyclopedia of Cognitive Science*. London: Macmillan Publishers.
6. Thomas, S. G., & Kamble, S. G. (2023). Forgiveness and its relationship with social connectedness and subjective well-being. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 11(4), 2492-2497.
7. Thompson, B., & Korsgaard, M.A. (2019). Relational Identification and Forgiveness: Facilitating Relationship Resilience. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 34, 153-167.
8. Toussaint, L., Worthington, E. L., Webb, J. R., Wilson, C., & Williams, D. R. (2023). Forgiveness in human flourishing. *Human flourishing*, 117.
9. Vismaya, A., Gopi, A., Romate, J., & Rajkumar, E. (2024). Psychological interventions to promote self-forgiveness: a systematic review. *BMC psychology*, 12(1), 258.
10. Bayat D. E., I. Asadpour, F. Mohsenzadeh, A. Kasaei. (2021). *Journal of Psychological Science*, Vol. 20, Issue 97, 139-151